

BEHAVIOR OF GFRP BARS SUBJECTED TO DYNAMIC LOADING

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Introduction

- Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) bars emerged as a substitute for steel rebars in concrete structures as they solve the corrosion problem of steel.
- FRP bars have attractive characteristics such as high strength to weight ratio and magnetic transparency.
- Extensive research examined different properties of FRP bars under tension.
- Current design codes forbid the use of FRP bars in compression members due to doubts about the performance of FRP bars in compression.
- Analysis of the available literature review shows that the contribution of FRP bars in compression should not be neglected [1-5].
- In this study, the behavior of Glass FRP (GFRP) bars subjected to impact loading at various loading rates is investigated. Confidence interval graphs were developed to identify the effect of different loading rates on the ultimate stress of the FRP bars.

Experimental Program

- Twenty one GFRP bars were tested with different diameters: 12, 17, 20, 27 mm.
- The GFRP bars were manufactured by Pultron Ltd Company (G0) and Galen Company (G1) shown in Fig.1.

Figure 1: GFRP bars before testing (a) G0 (b) G1

Figure 2: Dynamic Drop Mass Bench

- Drop hammer test used to conduct the dynamic tests as shown in Fig. 2.
- The force of the impact and displacement of the bars were recorded simultaneously through an acquisition chain.
- Weight of mass and height of fall varied to achieve different impact energies.

Results and Discussion

- As the rate of loading increased, the strength of the G1-D17 bars dropped, as shown in Fig.3 (a).
- As the rate of loading increased, the strength of the G1-D20 bars increased, shown in Fig.3 (b).

Figure 3: Confidence Interval Graphs of Maximum Stress Vs Loading Rate of (a) G1-D17 (b) G1-D20

- The G1-D12 reported an average stress of 367 MPa for a rate of loading equal to 166 s⁻¹, as depicted in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Confidence Interval Graph of Maximum Stress Vs Loading Rate of G1-D12

- All G0-D27 bars reported similar mean strength values even as loading rate increased, shown in Fig.5.

Figure 5: Confidence Interval Graph of Maximum Stress Vs Loading Rate of G0-D27

- The G0-D27 and G1-D17 bars changed shape from cylindrical to conical.
- The G1-D20 bars were crushed completely.
- All the GFRP bars failed due to the separation of the fibers as depicted in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: GFRP bars after testing (a) G1-D17 (b) G1-D20 (c) G1-D12 (d) G0-D27

Conclusion

- Impact dynamic tests were conducted on GFRP bars with different diameters using the drop hammer test at various rates.
- The strength of the G1-D17 bars decreased as the loading rate increased, which requires further investigation.
- The general failure of the GFRP bars was caused by the separation of the fibers.

References

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